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MOST COMMON EXPRESSIONS OF AGREEMENT AND DISAGREEMENT IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK

Abstract. In this article statement verbal and nonverbal communication is reflected by both isomorphic and different (allomorphic) characteristics in communicative situations in English and Uzbek expressions related to demonstrating consent and dissent. The national peculiarities of the expression of verbal and nonverbal consent and disagreement are revealed.

Key words: Verbal and nonverbal communication, speech act, expressions of agreement and disagreement, language levels, sociolinguistic factors.

Acting solely through speech is referred to as a speech act. Speaking allows us to do a wide range of tasks. Making a promise, asking a question, ordering or begging someone to do something, threatening, and so on are all examples of making a promise. Each of these examples represents a specific speaking act. "Requesting," "commanding," "questioning," "informing," "apologizing," "complaining," "promising," "complementing," or "inviting" are all examples of speaking acts. The activity done by a speaker with an utterance is known as a speech act. The British philosopher John L. Austin initially proposed the Speech Act Theory in the late 1930s (1911-1960). His student, American philosopher John Searle, further expanded the Theory. The Austrian philosopher Ludwig Wittgenstein's thoughts on language games foreshadowed the principles of Speech act theory. The speech act, according to Searle, is "the basic or simplest unit of linguistic communication". The symbol, word, or phrase is not the unit of linguistic communication, as is commonly assumed, but rather the production of the symbol, word, or sentence in the execution of the speech act.

According to the Contemporary Advanced English Dictionary, disagreement is a debate between persons who have opposing viewpoints on a topic. It can also refer to a failure to reach a consensus. Various meanings of disagreement were projected onto the screen by academics. According to Leech (2016), the pragmatic distinction between direct and indirect disagreement strategies is based on the presence of performative expressions and the matching of syntactic structure and semantic function. Disagreeing with others' viewpoints is an essential speech act that may be conveyed both verbally and nonverbally. Its linguistic manifestation may be seen at all levels of the language: lexical, grammatical (morphological and syntactical), and phraseological.

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The replicas-stimuli offered questions reflect the genuine phenomenon of modern spoken English, which is not based on strict grammar standards and book vocabulary. Questions reflect the current status of spoken phrases and conforming to the manner of agreeing and disagreeing. Gender, age, education, level of English (elementary, intermediate, advanced) professional, sociolinguistics factors were also taken into consideration.

The aforementioned elements have an impact on informants' level of proficiency and awareness of the current situation of spoken English. The table below shows quantitative information.

At all language levels, disagreement may be conveyed in a variety of ways as a form of speech act in dialogic discourse. According to the pragmatic meaning of disagreement and other sociolinguistic, pragmatic, and cultural aspects, the answer-reaction might be vocal or nonverbal, implicit or explicit. Sornig describes a speech act of dispute from the standpoint of Speech Act Theory as a response act to an act that comes before it; in other words, it necessitates a preceding utterance from an interlocutor. Within the context of speech act theories, disagreement is investigated as a communicative, illocutionary, and social act. “Disagreement is a speech act in which the speaker expresses an opinion or viewpoint that is partially or completely incompatible with the prior speaker's statement. To put it another way, agreement is often seen as the desirable and preferable alternative. Disagreement is seen as its negative, unfavorable counterpart”. All above mentioned information provide mostly theoretical background of expressing agreement and disagreement. Below there are examples of verbal expressions of agreement and disagreement in English by British council in order to help non-native speakers learn and use expressions correctly:

Agreeing	Disagreeing	Partially agreeing
<i>That's right!</i>	<i>I don't agree!</i>	<i>I agree up to a point, but...</i>
<i>Absolutely!</i>	<i>I totally disagree!</i>	<i>I see your point, but..</i>
<i>Exactly!</i>	<i>Absolutely not!</i>	<i>That's partly true...</i>
<i>Me too!</i>	<i>That's not right!</i>	<i>I'm not so sure about that</i>
<i>Yes, I agree!</i>	<i>I'm not sure about that.</i>	I understand your point, but...
<i>I totally agree!</i>	I completely disagree with you!	I agree with you up to a degree, but...
<i>I couldn't agree more!</i>	Certainly not!	That's partly true, but...
<i>I see exactly what you mean!</i>	That's not correct!	I'm not convinced.
<i>You're right. That's a good point.</i>	That is something I am not sure of.	I am a bit confused...
I (completely / really / totally / absolutely / honestly / truly) agree with you (on that)	I'm afraid...	That idea is OK, but...

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The next table provides Uzbek expressions demonstrating agreement and disagreement.

Rozilik	Rozi bo'lmalik/Qarshi fikr bildirish
<i>Siz haqsiz!</i>	<i>Bu fikrga qo'shilmayman.</i>
<i>Fikringizga qo'shilaman!</i>	<i>Men mutaqo qarshiman!</i>
<i>Men ham shuni aytmogchiydim!</i>	<i>Aslo yo'q!</i>
<i>To'g'ri!</i>	<i>Bu xato!</i>
<i>Albatta!</i>	<i>Ishonchim komil emas.</i>
<i>Mutlaqo haqsiz!</i>	Rozi emasman.
<i>Bundan yaxshisi bo'lmaydi!</i>	Qarshiman.
<i>Men ham shunday o'ylayman!</i>	To'g'ri emas!
<i>Tan olaman.</i>	Xato fikr.
Qrashiligim yo'q.	Men boshqacha fikrdaman
Men ham.	Kechirasiz-u, men fikrim....
<i>Men ham bu fikrga qo'shilaman.</i>	Ishonmayman!
<i>Nimani nazarda tutganingizni angladim.</i>	<i>Balki to'g'ridir, lekin...</i>
Yaxshi fikr bildirdingiz.	Ikki fikrlaymiz deb qo'rqaman....
<i>Bir xil fikrlar ekanmiz</i>	Men masalaga boshqa tomondan yondashaman.
Qarashlarimiz o'xshash ekan.	Bekor gap!
<i>Rad etishga ojizman.</i>	E'tirozim bor!
Ayni haqiqat.	Ma'qul emas.
Shunisi adolatdan.	Men noroziman.
Shubhasiz!	Siz nohaqsiz!
Mutlaqo to'g'ri.	Bu adolatdan emas!

Both in English and Uzbek verbal expressions of agreement and disagreement are demonstrated by single words or phrases. Most of them are translated directly and there is no difference in meaning. Especially, expressions of disagreement tend to be politely expressed in both languages. However, nonverbal expressions differ in meaning and some of them may even cause cultural misunderstandings. For example, in English culture, handshaking with strangers, especially women, shows the sign of respect towards the addressee. On the other hand, it is recommended to avoid this action, especially, with women. The same with the usage of eye contact. In Uzbek mentality, eye contact does not express respect or honesty. Uzbek EFL speakers use the same nonverbal means of expressing consent, for example, "nodding your head", "smile", and "handshaking".

Verbal communication is the most researched and widespread type of interpersonal communication. This is the most universal way of transmitting information, since verbal language is the main way of "translating" a message created using any other sign system. Verbal communication uses human speech, natural sound language, that is, a system of phonetic signs, as a sign system. Speech is investigated as the most universal mean of communication, since speech is used to encode and decode information. According to the traditional concept,

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verbal language was recognized as the main one in the transmission of communicative messages. Means of non-verbal communication did not play a significant role and were considered an addition to verbal language. However, the means of non-verbal communication have been used in various fields since ancient times. Verbal and nonverbal communication was investigated as sociocultural and linguocultural phenomenon. Theoretical data in English on basis of topic has been collected and compared with researches which were done by Uzbek scientists. Communication types, analytical-typological comparison of expressing agreement and disagreement, their types, characteristics of verbal and non-verbal communication, speech act, communication as a discipline, its benefits, theories and methods from previous research works have been found and analyzed.

The analysis allows us to draw the following conclusions. Speech acts of agreement and disagreement have a high frequency in dialogical interaction and represent modal categories expressing the speaker's attitude to the subject of speech and included in the corresponding semantic fields of agreement and disagreement. The speech act of consent reflects a positive attitude, in one way or another acceptance of the interlocutor's point of view and includes all means united by common semantic features and located in the core, center or periphery of the field of consent. The speech act of disagreement refers to all types of negative reaction in relation to the initiating remark – refutation, objection, judgment, expression of dissatisfaction, disapproval, etc., also included in a given semantic field. Disagreement by its nature affects the personal feelings of communicants more, because it is a negative reaction to the initiating statement. Verbal and nonverbal means of expressing disagreement tend to be more emotional and expressive than the means of expressing consent. It also sought to compile a list of cutting-edge techniques that can be used or modified to detect these cues.

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